

ORGANIZING PRIMARY EDUCATION PROCESS ON THE BASE OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES AND DEVELOPING CRITICAL AND CREATIVE THINKING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975170>

Abstract. *There is no doubt that the future of every country is in the hands of its youth. Therefore, the fundamental reform, renewal, enrichment of the education system, and the improvement of the level of knowledge of pedagogues working in this field remain one of the most urgent issues. Reform in any field is carried out on the basis of the principle of small to large, simple to complex. In particular, it is appropriate to start development in the field of education from preschool and primary education. In carrying out reforms, it is necessary to use the experience of developed foreign countries and popularize the recommendations of foreign and local pedagogues who have achieved great success and organize lessons in an exemplary manner. This thesis is based on the experience of developed foreign countries. The importance of using the characteristics of the organization of primary education is discussed.*

Keywords: *pedagogue, educational process, modernization, primary education, international experience, student knowledge, educational reform, development, higher educational institution, competence, students' knowledge, modern technologies, intelligence, spiritual potential.*

It is very important that there are more and more countries around the world that are achieving many successes with their educational systems and programs. Great Britain has a special place among them. Britain, in their schools, teachers are assigned the same general program, but the teacher can adopt it by adding his own strategies. Educators should from the relationship between the students and themselves right from the beginning. For this,

Take time to get to know students and listen to them.

A good educator tries to understand their students and their individual learning needs. Developing strong relationship with elementary school students is critical. Because all subsequent processes are based on these relationships. It is also important to create an atmosphere of mutual respect. True, working with each of the students individually and trying to hear them takes a lot of time. But through this, it is possible to achieve that students show their “best abilities”.

Know the difference between formative and summative assessment.

Formative assessment is a continuous assessment by the teacher aimed at determining the extent to which students have understood the subject.

Examples: “One-minute paper” method, i.e. the teacher gives students one minute at the end of the lesson. In this, students explain what they understand and what they don’t understand about the topic.

“Sharing in groups” in which at the end of the lesson, the teacher asks the students to summarize the lessons. The students share their thoughts in front of the group. Students’ ability to speak in front of the team also formed.

Summative assessments are an assessment of student learning and achievement by comparing it to standard on benchmark. Summative assessments have a high score.

Examples: “Final exam” where the teachers take an exam from the students at the end of each quarter or semester. The form of the exam is chosen by the teacher.

Encouragement and recognition.

The effort spent by the teacher to make the students complete the task it must be shown that it will be rewarded. A teacher can promote active learning by recognizing those who try hard, rather than focusing on those who do it right.

Formation of critical and creative thinking skills.

In this, the teacher asks students questions about the studied topics. That is, the student is asked to approach each issue, situation and problem critically and creatively. For example, at the end of a story or a fairy tale:

Why did the course of events end this way?

What would you do if you were the main character?

If you were a writer, how would you end the story (fairy tale) and why?
asking questions like.

“Metacognition” is thinking about thinking.

A widely recognized teaching method for primary school students, it is mainly based on questioning students’ thinking and reasoning skills and encouraging them to self- assess and self-involves encouraging self-reflection.

Application: after the teacher teaches the basic concepts and skills of a specific topic, students ask themselves questions such as:

refers to:

- What concepts were I aware of before this topic was covered?
- What did I learn today?
- How did I learn this?
- Where and for what can I use this knowledge?
- What else do I need to learn?

It is precisely such questions that students think critically and creatively serves as a basis for developing skills.

The best teaching methods for primary school.

“Cooperative learning”. Group work is a cooperative learning strategy that allows students with various learning levels together. Cooperative lesson plans include projects that involve group work, partner learning, of teacher- student work. This method can be extremely

beneficial for struggling students, it also gives the teacher the ability to identify and target students that need extra attention.

“Flipped classroom” is a teaching strategy where pupils are introduced to learning content before the lessons (for example, through homework, pre-reading, and etc.). Flipped classroom examples include students watching video lessons before class and using their in-class time for discussion, problem-solving.

Modeling. Teachers can use a modeling teaching strategy by generating their own example as an acceptable answer. For some students, it’s easier to learn when you tell them what to do and then show them how to do it. This teaching method will be especially helpful for students who identify themselves as visual learners. Among younger age groups, you may model appropriate classroom behaviors.

Differentiation is a teaching strategy that lets you assign tasks to students based on their specific academic abilities and their learning needs. Effective classrooms are often inclusive settings so it’s important to teach to a range of learning levels simultaneously. Here some ways to use differentiation:

- Provide books or other materials at different reading levels
- Create custom spelling lists for students with different spelling skills
- Host small groups to provide tailored advice to students.
- Offer one-on-one after school help to students encountering challenges.
- Measure progress in different ways, through projects, portfolios and participation.

In conclusion, it should be said that every pedagogue should work tirelessly on himself. Using the experience of developed foreign countries the organization of classes is very effective.

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